
EDGE SpAIce: ENABLING ONBOARD DATA COMPRESSION WITH MACHINE LEARNING ON FPGAs

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ABSTRACT

In the past decade, AI driven algorithms have tremendously increased the reliability in object detection cases for both standard computer vision problems and earth observation image products. Meanwhile, use cases have started to emerge for which a downlink bandwidth limitation should be avoided, for example Space Situation Awareness. This has generated a need for on board AI processing. Earth observation use cases requiring fast responses are also emerging and pushing for reliable algorithms on board, that is to say Deep Neural Networks (e.g. flood detection or early wildfire detection). Consequently, there is a growing need for efficient data processing and compression. Tailoring onboard processing with Machine Learning to specific mission tasks can optimise downlink usage by focusing only on relevant data, ultimately reducing the required bandwidth. The Edge SpAIce project showcases onboard data filtering and reduction by using Deep Learning to identify plastic litter in the oceans. The deployment pipeline, including drastic model compression and deployment using the open-source `hls4ml` and `QONNX` tools, enables high-performance, low-power, low-cost computation on onboard FPGA processors. We present lab-based demonstration results, highlighting performance in terms of accuracy, throughput, and power consumption, and discuss planned deployment aspects.

1 Introduction

The increasingly high fidelity of on-board imaging, coupled with the increasing deployment of small satellite missions introduces a data bottleneck for the conventional approach of transmitting all data to ground stations. Meanwhile, the increasing compute power available on-board introduces the possibility of performing fast and accurate data reduction with on-board processing. Since most of the data capture during Earth observation are obscured by clouds, a significant bandwidth saving can be achieved if clouds can be reliably identified on-board. Furthermore, a given mission may only be seeking to capture imagery of specific surface objects that are rare compared to the majority. Even more significant bandwidth reductions can be realised if a mission is given the autonomy to filter and transmit only relevant images.

In this work we use Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to segment satellite images into different object classes, deployed onto an AMD System-on-Chip device. The Neural Networks are first reduced in parameter size compared to an unconstrained offline model, into a smaller model suitable for onboard deployment within the device resource and power envelope.

For FPGA deployment we utilise the `hls4ml` library [1], a technology originally developed for the hardware triggers of experiments of the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) at CERN to demonstrate the potential of onboard AI processing. In those experiments, particle collisions occur at a rate of 40 MHz, with each collision producing around 1 MB of data. This overwhelming stream can only be processed by selecting the most interesting events in real time. A first stage of data filtering is implemented on FPGAs to very quickly decide whether each collision event should be kept or discarded. Events that are kept will be subsequently reprocessed in much more detail offline. This two-stage approach massively reduces the amount of data that needs to be processed with high precision and high compute cost.

Analogously, we propose a processing pipeline that can be deployed on-board satellites for Earth Observation to filter images. Depending on the mission, each image captured by the sensors on a satellite may not capture the objects of interest, or the image may be obscured by clouds. Sending all images to the surface for processing and identification will utilise most of the bandwidth transmitting images that are ultimately discarded. Instead, we demonstrate the per-pixel labelling (segmentation) of images into different classes of interest, using Neural Networks implemented on FPGAs that can be deployed on-board. Segmented images could be filtered based on the prevalence of specific classes, or the presence of clouds. We do not demonstrate the filtering step of the pipeline in this work, which is expected to be mission dependent. Images that are selected by the on-board processor can of course be additionally compressed, whether by classical or AI approaches.

This paper is organised as follows: Section 2 describes other related work; Section 3 describes the dataset used; Section 4 describes the training, quantisation, and representation of Neural Networks for clouds labelling; Section 5 describes the deployment of these Neural Network models onto FPGAs; Section 6 presents the performance of these models measured on the target FPGA.

2 Related Work

Other works have demonstrated the use of Neural Networks for data reduction in the context of processing onboard satellites. In [2] the authors train CNNs to classify $28 \times 28 \times 3$ patches of images as containing or not containing clouds, deployed onto an Intel Neural Compute Stick 2, Critical Link MitySOM-5CSx, and Google Coral Edge TPU. AMD FPGA SoC devices (Zynq Ultrascale+, Zynq 7000 series), AMD Kintex Ultrascale KU04, AMD G-Series and Intel Myriad 2 were benchmarked with CNNs trained for image segmentation in Earth observation in [3]. [4] provides a comprehensive summary of the specific opportunities and challenges arising from the possibility of onboard image processing with AI, including improved efficiency.

In the context of semantic segmentation, `hls4ml` has been successfully utilised to process images for autonomous vehicles [5], using aggressive pruning and quantization at training time [6].

3 Dataset

We have used the ALCD dataset [7] of clouds collected from Sentinel-2 images to train Neural Networks for this work. The original images of the dataset comprises 31 images, of size $10980 \times 10980 \times 3$ where the final dimension are the RGB channels. Before training NN models, we cropped the images to dimensions $512 \times 512 \times 3$. For performance and resource consumption reasons, we further crop the images to size $256 \times 256 \times 3$ for inference. The input image is further preprocessed with normalisation. Truth labels are provided per-pixel with 2 classes: clouds and background.

4 Neural Network Training and Compression

We train Neural Networks for image segmentation, that is predicting the label of each pixel in the image. For this task we use the UNet architecture [8], which reduces the image size to a bottleneck using successive Convolutional layers, followed by Upsampling from the bottleneck back to the original image dimensions for the pixel predictions.

4.1 Quantization Aware Training

For FPGA deployment, integer or fixed-point arithmetic operations are preferred over floating-point, resulting in much reduced resource usage and latency. We use the technique of Quantization Aware Training (QAT) for reducing the required precision of the models to be deployed with `hls4ml`. QAT has been demonstrated to enable training of Neural Networks that have practically the same performance as those trained with floating point precision, but with significantly reduced integer bitwidths [6, 9–11]. In this work we use the Brevitas library from AMD [12] for the model QAT, and QONNX for the export format [13, 14]. QONNX is an extension to the widely used ONNX format, adding support for arbitrary quantisation of any tensor of a model.

The dataflow architecture of `hls4ml` enables heterogeneous quantisation, that is that each tensor (weight, bias, or between layers) may be quantised independently of any other. This contrasts with other compute architecture for Neural Networks that reuse one, or several, arithmetic units for all computations, requiring instead homogeneous quantisation of the model. Brevitas also supports heterogeneous quantisation of a model, where the precision is a learnable parameter during the training.

Figure 1: Example images from the ALCD dataset: RGB image (left), pixel labels (right)

4.2 Knowledge Distillation

In order to reduce the size of the actual DNN running on the hardware, we train a teacher Neural Network, and distill it into a much smaller student model, the process of Knowledge Distillation [15]. This approach is quite straight-forward and uses the logits of a teacher model (continuous values) instead of the ground truth data (binary values) to train a student DNN. Traditionally, the weights and feature maps of the student model are in the same type as the ones of the teacher model (that is 32 bits floating point values). Then, a quantization step is required to deploy on a given hardware. Here we directly train the student model using quantization, leaving only the compilation part after ingestion of the student quantized model to `hls4ml`. This procedure generally allows us to reduce the number of free parameters of a model by a factor 50-160, making them usable with existing middle-ware compilation and deployment tools such as AMD's Vitis AI or `hls4ml`.

4.3 QONNX

QONNX (Quantised ONNX) [14] is an extension of the ONNX open format, born to represent and exchange machine learning and deep learning models. The format defines an extensible computational graph and include definitions of operators and data types. QONNX extends ONNX by introducing the concept of quantisation in the computational graph as an operator, represented as a node in the computational graph. In order to maintain the values in the floating point 32-bit format across

Figure 2: The figure schematize the structure of the UNet model used in this work.

the computational graph, the quantisation is applied following the Quantize-Clip-Dequantize (QCDQ) schema; the different parts of the aforementioned schema are described by the following equations:

$$y = \text{quantise}(x) = \text{clamp}(\text{round}(\frac{x}{s} + z), y_{min}, y_{max}) \quad (1)$$

where x is the floating-point input tensor to quantise, s is the scale the output quantised tensor, z is the zero-point or quantization bias coefficient. The function round , can be round-to-even or round-to-zero, and clamp performs clipping inclusive of the boundaries y_{min} and y_{max} . These boundaries are defined as

$$y_{min} = \begin{cases} -2^{n_b-1} & \text{if signed} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

$$y_{max} = \begin{cases} 2^{n_b-1} - 1 & \text{if signed} \\ 2^{n_b} - 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $n_b \geq 2$ is the bit width of the output quantised tensor, and “signed” defines its signedness. To compute the floating-point representation of a quantised value, the dequantise operator is implemented as

$$\text{dequantise}(y) = s \times (y - z) \quad (4)$$

where y is a quantised tensor, z is its zero-point and s its scale. The model analysed in this work implemented the quantisation by using ‘Quant’ nodes from QONNX library. The behaviour of the ‘Quant’ node is explained by the equations 1 and 4. For more details refer to [13].

For this work we trained UNet model with a structure shown in 2. The first part of the model – which performs Downsampling – reduces the spatial dimensions of the tensors, increasing the number of filters. After reaching the bottleneck, in which the tensor size reaches the spatial dimensions of 16x16, the second part of the model – which performs Upsampling – increases the spatial dimensions and concatenate the tensors coming from the bottleneck path with the ones produced by skip connections coming from the Downsampling part. The input of the model is an RGB image with dimensions $256 \times 256 \times 3$ pixels. The output is a segmented image with dimensions $256 \times 256 \times 2$. We trained a model with 50×10^3 trainable parameters (weights and biases), now referred to as “50k”. The model considered has been trained using quantisation-aware training, fixing the quantisation of the weight and activation tensors of the network to 4 bits. In order to convert the model from QONNX to hls4ml, it is necessary to transform the model into the channels last format. A tensor in a channels last format assume the shape $(H \times W \times C)$, where H is the height in pixels of the image, W is the width in pixels of the image and C is the number of channels of the image. hls4ml in fact currently only supports models in channels last form for implementation and performance reasons.

5 Deployment on FPGA

Inference of the trained, distilled and quantised Neural Networks described in Section 4 was carried out using the two tools Vitis AI and hls4ml. Each tool provides a workflow to map the model onto hardware primitives. The key difference

between the tools is that the hardware architecture of Vitis AI is a Data Processing Unit (DPU) onto which the model is deployed, while `hls4ml` is a dataflow architecture which constructs a hardware description of a specific provided model. A Xilinx ZCU102 development kit, which hosts a XCZU9EG-2FFVB1156 MPSoC device, was used for all throughput and latency measurements.

5.1 Vitis AI

As a baseline for comparison with a commercial solution, we used Vitis AI [16], a development environment that can be leveraged to accelerate AI inference on AMD FPGAs. Vitis AI uses a reprogrammable engine with a specialised instruction set called Deep-Learning Processing Unit (DPU). A single DPU instance loaded on the PL enables the deployment of multiple CNNs without reloading a new bitstream. Vitis AI compiles an executable that can be uploaded to the DPU for each network.

The software image was provided by AMD as a Vitis-AI pre-built image for the ZCU102. The image includes a 3-core Deep Learning Unit (DPU) of the DPUCZDX8G architecture on the Programmable Logic (PL). Each core is capable of 4096 peak operations per cycle.

The quantization step for each model was executed using the Vitis AI PyTorch workflow. All weights and biases were quantised to 8 bit integers, using a set of 100 calibration images to derive appropriate scalings from the floating point model weights.

5.2 `hls4ml`

We targeted the open-source software `hls4ml` [1] to deploy the previously described Neural Networks. `hls4ml` is a source-to-source compile that converts Neural Networks into High Level Synthesis (HLS) code that can be synthesized for an FPGA. In particular for this work we make use of the Convolutional Neural Network and Image Segmentation features introduced in [17] and [5]. For this deployment, a Neural Network is first converted into an `hls4ml` model representation, providing a configuration specifying parallelisation parameters. These together are used to produce an HLS project that can be synthesized through the AMD FPGA tool suite Vitis HLS and Vivado. A full accelerator architecture is provided by `hls4ml`, targeting a runtime using the `pynq` package from AMD [18]. Since `hls4ml` maps each NN layer and operation onto independent logic modules in the FPGA, the model size is capped by the available resources on the device.

5.2.1 FIFO Depth Optimization

With its dataflow architecture, `hls4ml` requires a FIFO buffer between each NN layer compute unit in order to synchronise the logic blocks. The required depth of each FIFO depends on the specific pattern of data produced and consumed by consecutive layers, which in turn depends on the latency and initiation interval of the synthesized modules. As such, it is not possible to anticipate the required depth from a static analysis of the NN architecture ahead of compilation. To address this, `hls4ml` sets the default FIFO size to match the input tensor size for each layer as a worst case for a single input, while the width is equal to the number of channels. An undersized FIFO will cause a slowdown of the inference as the computation must stall to allow the FIFO to drain, while an oversized FIFO will over utilize memory resource, reducing the model size that can fit within a given FPGA resource envelope.

In order to find the minimum required depth of each FIFO, which produces the smallest resource usage for a given NN while ensuring that there will be no stalling of the compute during inference, we utilize a procedure termed “FIFO Depth Optimization”, first introduced in [5]. In this work we have further developed the FIFO Depth Optimization by adapting it to the Vitis HLS toolchain. Figure 3, illustrates the optimization results for trained model, where most FIFO depths after optimization are near one and significantly smaller than their initial values. In the default configuration set by `hls4ml`, FIFO depths are larger in the first and last layers, while smaller in the central layers due to the U-Net architecture. Figure 4 shows the floorplan of a model with 10×10^3 parameters implemented with `hls4ml` for the target XCZU9EG-2FFVB1156 device before and after FIFO depth optimization. The significant reduction in BRAMs used is clearly visible in the floorplans. A model with 10k parameters was used for this comparison since it is unable to place the larger parameter size model in the target device before the optimization.

A second optimization introduced in this work for the purpose of minimising the FIFO depths is to reduce the latency of individual layer modules as much as possible. While reducing the latency of a layer often comes at the expense of higher resource usage for the computation of the layer, it may also reduce the depth of the FIFO required to buffer its output data, making an overall saving. Since BRAMs were found to be the limiting FPGA resource in the deployment of the considered model architecture, this saving enabled larger models to be executed on the device with `hls4ml`.

Figure 3: FIFO depths of the CNN before and after FIFO Depth Optimization.

(a) Before FIFO Depth optimisation

(b) After FIFO Depth optimisation

Figure 4: Floorplan of a 10k parameters model before and after FIFO Depth Optimization. Block RAMS, the resource primarily used for FIFOs, are shown in bright green. The significant reduction in BRAM usage is visible in the floorplan. The floorplan highlights the different layers of the network: pink for concatenate, yellow for leaky ReLU, orange for pooling, red for resize, blue for convolution, purple for zero-padding, and brown for the U-Net branching.

6 Results

The accuracy of the deployed model can be found in Table 1. The Mean IoU metric quantifies the overlap between the predicted segmented region and the ground truth annotated region from a dataset. The Mean F1-score is calculated from the precision and recall of the test, where the precision is the number of true positive results divided by the number of all

samples predicted to be positive, including those not identified correctly, and the recall is the number of true positive results divided by the number of all samples that should have been identified as positive. The results are taken from the Brevitas validation phase.

Table 1: Accuracy scores of the cloud segmentation model.

Mean IoU	Mean F1-score
0.818	0.897

Table 2 shows the FPGA resource usage of the the h1s4m1 and Vitis AI implementations. The h1s4m1 implementation allocates more Look up Tables (LUTs) and Flip Flops (FFs), but fewer Block RAMs (BRAMs) and Digital Signal Processors (DSPs) compared to the DPU that has a constant resource utilisation regardless of the model deployed.

Table 2: Resource utilisation comparison measured on the ZCU102 development kit, extracted from the Vivado implementation. Reprogramming the DPU does not change the bitstream, thus the resource utilisation does not depend on the number of parameters of the model.

Platform	LUT	LUTRAM	FF	BRAM	DSP
h1s4m1	251396 (92%)	20323 (14%)	114324 (21%)	374 (41%)	246 (10%)
Vitis AI	163166 (60%)	20782 (14%)	303801 (12%)	769 (84%)	2144 (85%)

Table 3 shows the compute performance of h1s4m1 and Vitis AI on the model inference. We measure the image processing framerate and the power consumption of the full SoC board combined, during the processing burst, to compute the key metric of pixels per second per Watt. The h1s4m1 deployment of the NNs operates at a higher framerate and lower power usage than the Vitis AI deployment. The 50k model is deployed with 8.8 times higher pixels per second per Watt with h1s4m1 than with Vitis AI. This performance gain originates primarily from the core of h1s4m1 implementation, where weights are stored on-chip rather than being fetched from the DDR memory, which reduces both power consumption and memory bottlenecks.

Table 3: Inference performance of the cloud segmentation model, deployed with either h1s4m1 or Vitis AI, measured on the ZCU102 development kit.

Platform	Framerate (FPS)	Power (W)	pixels/s/W($\cdot 10^6$)
h1s4m1	834.3	3.9	14.2
Vitis AI	287.5	11.8	1.6
Ratio h1s4m1/Vitis AI	2.9	0.3	8.8

7 Conclusion

In this work we introduced a pipeline to deploy image segmentation Neural Networks onto onboard FPGAs. The deployment pipeline comprises knowledge distillation to shrink a model to a size suitable for resource-constrained deployment; quantization-aware training for further improved mapping onto hardware; QONNX for quantized model representation; and h1s4m1 with FIFO Depth Optimization for compilation of Neural Networks to FPGA targets. Taking advantage of the h1s4m1 dataflow architecture, we demonstrated a performance improvement of a factor 8.8 over the Vitis AI tool. In future work we plan to extend the h1s4m1 tool to deploy NNs with more parameters and better classification performance to the same device.

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